

Formulation And Evaluation of Ondansetron Hydrochloride Medicated Jelly

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ABSTRACT

Ondansetron medicated jelly is an emerging oral drug delivery system developed to enhance patient compliance and provide rapid therapeutic action. Ondansetron is a highly effective antiemetic agent, extensively utilized to treat and prevent nausea and vomiting resulting from various causes, including chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and postoperative recovery. It prevents 5-HT from depolarizing vagal afferents in the G.I.T., NTS, and CTZ through 5-HT₃ receptors. Compared to liquid dose forms, it is easier to administer to children. This formulation is an excellent substitute for administering medication to elderly, dysphagic, and paediatric patients. They provide considerable benefits over both liquid and solid dosage forms because they change into a liquid-like state a few seconds to a minute after being administered and stay solid during storage, which helps with dosage form stability. Oral jellies therefore offer a great deal of potential to be used as a delivery strategy for most medications in the near future.

Keywords: Oral medicated jelly, Ondansetron HCl, Heating and congealing, Antiemetic, Gelling agent..

INTRODUCTION

Ondansetron, the prototype of a new class of antiemetic drugs, was developed to control vomiting caused by radiation and chemotherapy. It was later discovered to be very successful in treating postoperative nausea and vomiting. It stops 5-HT from depolarizing via 5-HT₃ receptors on vagal afferents in the G.I.T., NTS, and CTZ. Even though ondansetron comes in a variety of dose forms, including tablets, oral disintegrating tablets, syrups, and injections, swallowing traditional solid dosage forms continues to be a significant difficulty for dysphagic, elderly, and paediatric patients[1]. Medicated oral jellies have evolved as a novel, patient-friendly medication delivery method that offers improved palatability, quick disintegration, convenience of administration, and increased compliance in order to get around these restrictions.

By reducing first pass metabolism, these prepared jellies have higher bioavailability. The gelling ingredient was dissolved in water to create jellies The

oral cavity is where many medicinal substances are absorbed. Compared to conventional oral dosage forms, medicated jelly and chewing gum provide quicker therapeutic action for medications with substantial buccal absorption. Both systemic disorders and oral cavity problems can be treated locally using medicated jelly. The jelly formulation has several benefits, including a pleasant mouth feel, quicker breakdown, convenience of administration without water, and partial buccal absorption that can lower first-pass metabolism. Ondansetron's quick dissolution and beginning of action are guaranteed when it is included into a jelly matrix, which is essential during severe episodes of vomiting. To improve stability and taste, the formulation usually includes sweeteners, flavoring agents, and preservatives in addition to gelling agents like pectin, HPMC, or sodium CMC. All things considered, ondansetron medicated jelly is a viable strategy for enhancing therapeutic results in antiemetic therapy since it is a patient-friendly and efficient substitute for traditional oral dosage forms [1,2,3].

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ONDANSETRON**Figure:1 Structure of Ondansetron****USES**

- Ondansetron is an antiemetic 5-HT₃ antagonist (5-HT₃-receptor antagonist).
- It is used to treat nausea and vomiting brought on by radiation and cytotoxic chemotherapy.
- Postoperative nausea and vomiting are also prevented and treated with it.
- Regarding the treatment of nausea and vomiting, 5HT₃ antagonists play a crucial role [3,4].

ELLY

Drug delivery systems based on jelly have become popular as a flexible and patient-friendly dose form that has many benefits over traditional oral formulations. Pharmaceutical jellies are semi-solid, gelatinous formulations that are intended to deliver active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) orally. They offer better palatability, quick beginning of action, and convenience of administration [1,5]. They are particularly well-suited for dysphagic, elderly, and juvenile patients who frequently have trouble swallowing tablets or capsules because of their pleasant mouthfeel and soft texture.

For medications that are vulnerable to first-pass metabolism or gastric degradation, these formulations allow for homogenous dispersion of medications inside a polymeric matrix, guaranteeing improved stability, consistent dosage, and improved bioavailability. The functional possibilities of medicated jellies have been further increased by

advances in polymer science, such as the use of natural gums, synthetic polymers, and mucoadhesive agents. These advancements allow for controlled release, improved solubility of poorly water-soluble medications, and preservation of sensitive molecules [3,6].

Medicated jellies have become more well-known in therapeutic fields such nutraceutical delivery, analgesics, antiemetics, antihistamines, and antiallergics in recent years. Researchers and pharmaceutical producers have been inspired to investigate jelly formulations as a possible alternative platform for creative drug delivery due to their straightforward manufacturing procedure, low cost, and good patient compliance. The goal of this review is to give a thorough understanding of the formulation elements, polymers utilized, drug incorporation techniques, evaluation criteria, stability issues, and potential future developments of pharmaceutical dosage forms based on jelly [4,8].

IDEAL CHARACTERISTICS

1. Jellies are naturally hygroscopic.
2. Jellies are not fragile and can be transported.
3. Jellies can cover up the taste of bitter drugs and are compatible with them.
4. After a while, jelly leaves no trace in the oral cavity and is compatible with a pleasant mouthfeel.
5. The excipients and pharmacological properties have little to no impact on the jelly oral disintegration [4,8].

ADVANTAGES

1. Because it doesn't require water and may be used anywhere, at any time, ondansetron jelly is simple to administer.
2. The course of treatment may be stopped at any moment if necessary.
3. It might work especially well for the systemic administration of medications that are prone to hepatic or intestinal wall metabolism.

4. These drugs are released from the jelly and consumed, will either dissolve or suspend in saliva as they reach the digestive system, making them readily accessible.
5. It offers the ability to address the issues of short-lived action and fluctuations in drug release and retention times as a systemic drug delivery method through the oral mucosa.

DISADVANTAGES

1. Because it is an aqueous formulation, appropriate packaging is necessary to ensure drug stability and safety.
2. It may leave an unpleasant aftertaste if improperly prepared.
3. A number of stability issues arise as a result of syneresis, which extracts water from the gel.
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TYPES OF JELLIES

Medicated jellies

Medicated jellies are generally used on the mucosal layer as well as on the skin also they have spermicidal,

local anesthetics and antiseptic properties. They can hold adequate amount water and, on the evaporation, it gives a quite cooling effect, and they form residual film over skin which provides protection from foreign materials.

Lubricating jellies

This kind of jelly was created primarily to lubricate diagnostic tools like surgical gloves, catheters, and cystoscopes.

Miscellaneous jellies

Miscellaneous jellies are created for a variety of uses, including electrocardiography and patch testing.

- **Patch testing**

In this test, allergens are transported by jellies, which can be affixed to the skin's outermost layer to identify sensitivity and aid in particle separation.

- **Electro-cardiography**

Electrode jelly can be used in this test to lower the electrical resistance between the patient's skin and the cardiograph electrodes. Sodium chloride is applied to the skin's surface to provide good conductivity, and then pumice powder is applied to remove the skin's horny layer, which serves as an electrical resistance barrier.

Sweetening agent

Sucrose

Because of its hydrophilic and cost-effective qualities in its purest form, it is the most favored sweetener. Its chemical and physical characteristics remain constant throughout a range of pH values [9].

Saccharin

It is highly soluble and stable in water. However, when used in excess, it produces a metallic or harsh aftertaste.

Dextrose

Chemically, it exists in both anhydrous and monohydrate forms; the anhydrous form exhibits hygroscopic properties. In the different formulations, dextrose has 70% more sweetening power than sucrose.

Sucralose

It is created as an artificial sweetener by substituting three -OH- groups (hydroxyl) with -Cl- (chlorine) atoms in the sucrose molecule's structure. It is roughly 320–1,000 times sweeter than sucrose, twice as sweet as saccharin, and three times sweeter than aspartame. It has a slower start of sweetness than sucrose, although it can last longer.

Sorbitol

is both an isomeric form of mannitol and an alcoholic sweetener. Compared to sucrose, it is roughly 60% sweeter. It is utilized as a humectant in cosmetics and has thickening properties. Soft gel capsules are developed using it. It comes in crystalline form for direct compression processes as well as Sorb Tab.

Mannitol

Mannitol, a white crystalline polyol, is produced when fructose is hydrogenated. It is around 50% as sweet as sucrose. It has a free hydrophilic property because of the negative heat of mixture. It either entirely dissolves in the oral cavity after intake or produces a rather cool feeling when chewed [4,10].

Coloring agents

Uses of coloring agents

- To create an attractive appearance for goods.
- Aid in the identification and distinction of pharmaceutical formulations.
- Enhance patient compliance.

Types of coloring agents

Natural colors

These colorants can be manufactured chemically as lycopene and β -carotene, or they can be extracted from natural sources.

Mineral colors

Flesh color is produced by mineral hues, such as a mixture of ferric oxides, primarily red and yellow.

Dyes

These kinds of colorants are artificial chemical substances that, if fully dissolved in an appropriate solvent like glycerin or propylene glycol, provide color. Eighty to ninety-three percent of it is pure color. For instance, methylene blue, safranin, and crystal violet.

Flavoring agent

Flavoring agents can be used to cover up a product's bitter taste. This makes it feasible to increase patient compliance. Flavoring agents come in five different varieties: acidic (orange, lemon, cherry), alkaline (vanilla, chocolate, mint), bitter (orange, fennel, lemon), metallic (grape, berry), and sweet (honey, chocolate, raspberry, mastic, mint).

Preservatives

Jellies are typically prone to microbial development because they are primarily found in aqueous forms. Even though clay and cellulose derivatives inhibit the growth of microorganisms, preservation is crucial for limiting chemical moiety incompatibility and other excipients such gelling agents that have an impact on product shelf life [9,10,11].

Stabilizers

These are typically added to formulations to preserve key qualities and prevent incompatibilities over the product's shelf life. Sorbitol and propylene glycol are typically utilized. Chelating agents can be used to prevent drug incompatibilities with other formulation ingredients.

Gelling agents

Hydrocolloids are typically utilized as jellifying agents to create a matrix that resembles gel. To

dissolve in the liquid phase, colloid-based dissolving gelling agents form an internal structure that is primarily weakly cohesive.

Gelating agents includes,

Natural

Guar gum

It is taken from the seeds of the Leguminosae plant, *Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*. The endosperm section contains hydrophilic gum, which is utilized to thicken, emulsify, and stabilize different goods. It can swell or dissolve in polar solvents and make strong H⁺ bonds with them, but in non-polar solvents in particular, it can form weaker H⁺ bonds than in polar solvents.

Locust bean gum

The endosperm of carob seeds can be used to make what is also known as carob bean gum. The two processes of the carob gum isolation method are removing the husk from the seeds and treating them chemically or thermos mechanically. After the shell is separated, the germ is separated from the endosperm by splitting the seeds based on their length. Endosperm is then put through the grinding, sieving, grading, and packaging processes before being sold for a variety of uses.

Tamarind gum

The seeds of *Tamarindus indica* L. are used to make tamarind gum. Mature pod seeds are pulverized and milled using a mesh. Next, add the ground tamarind seeds to bidistilled water while stirring constantly. Once the mixture has boiled to 80°C, set it aside to separate the mucilage. Centrifuge the resultant mixture; the mucilage content is represented by the supernatant; filter the mixture and store the mucilage in a dry, cool location [12].

Konjac

Konjac glucomannan is a hydrophilic polymer that is extracted from konjac tubers. In the human body, α -mannase may be in charge of hydrolization in the colon and last segment of the small intestine. Konjac is primarily prepared as a jellifying agent by processing alkaline, cross-linking borate,

compounding polymer, preparing an electric field at high voltage, and cross-linking metal ions after modification.

Tara gum

It is the least expensive substitute for locust and gum guar. It is separated from the endosperm of Tara seeds (*Caesalpinia spinosa*) via a mechanical separation procedure.

Extrudates

Gum Arabic

Acacia senegal (Hashab gum) and *Acacia seyal* (talh gum) are producers of commercially viable gum arabic. The Sudanese Savanna belt is home to *Acacia seyal* var. *seyal* (talh).

Tragacanth

Gum tragacanth is made from members of the *Astragalus* genus. Common species that produce tragacanth include *A. gummifer*, *A. parrowianus*, *A. flucosus*, *A. rahensis*, *A. gossy pinus*, and *A. microcephalus*. Gum tragacanth comes in two shapes: ribbon and flakes. The vertical incisions produce flake-shaped gum exudates that resemble grains, while the horizontal and diagonal incisions mostly produce ribbon-shaped gum.

Gum Karaya

The plant known as Karaya (*Sterculia Urens*) is a member of the Malvaceae family. Karaya gum is the hardest to dissolve because of its acid stability. Although colloidal particles are not hydrophilic, they can collect water and cause the liquid to freeze by expanding up to 60 times their initial volume. Because of the acetyl groups in its structure, it might swell.

Microbial polysaccharides

Xanthan gum

Xanthan gum is a microbial polymer that is produced when *Xanthomonas campestris* ferments glucose. Other names include Rhodi gel, vanzan NF, gum corn, keltrol, and polysaccharide B-1459. It is utilized as a

stabilizer in emulsion and suspension compositions in addition to its gelling ability.

Gellan gum

It is extracted from *Pseudomonas elodea* as an anionic deacetylated exo-polysaccharide with tetrasaccharide repeating units of one α -L-rhamnose, one β -D glucuronic acid, and two β -D glucose units.

Dextran gum

Dextranase, a bacterial enzyme, is used to separate dextran from sucrose. Microorganisms that are helpful for the preparation include *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, and *Lactobacillus sanfrancisco*.

Curdlan

Alcaligenes faecalis var *myxo-genes* is the source of curdlan. The microbiological production of curdlan is carried out by soil bacteria. Curdlan is produced by the gram negative, non-pathogenic rod-shaped bacterium *Agrobacterium* species. Additionally, *Agrobacterium fabrum*, which is isolated from the nodules of leguminous plants, primarily groundnut and pea plants, was employed in its manufacturing.

Animal extract

Gelatin

Gelatin is a naturally occurring polymer that results from the hydrolytic breakdown of collagen and proteins. It contains two forms of gelatin: type A, which is an acidic gelatin with an isoelectrical point between 6 and 9, and type B, which is an alkaline gelatin with an isoelectrical point of 5 and is derived from collagen degradation. Bovine and pig gelatin are removed [12,13].

Collagen

Collagen is found in both vertebrates and invertebrates and differs from one another in terms of sequence, structure, and function. To maintain the stability and characteristics of the tissue and body, each substance is thus dispersed differently in the

skin, bones, tendons, arteries, or intramuscular connective tissue.

Semi-synthetic gelling agents

Modified polysaccharides

Propylene glycol esterification affects the gelation properties of gels; electrostatic association and hydrogen bonding cause weak gels to form quickly. Alginate has the ability to generate temperature-independent gels, in contrast to other polysaccharides like gelatin or agar. There are two ways to create alginate gels: acid precipitation (acidic gels) or ionic cross-linking with cations (ionic gels).

Cellulose based polymers

It is a common natural biopolymer. These kinds of polymers are abundant in plants, natural fibers, cotton, hardwoods or softwoods, linen, jute, and hemp; they can also be produced by fungus and are present in animals. Cellulose, a fiber made from macromolecules containing hundreds of glucose molecules, is produced by plants. They are divided into charged ionic (anionic and cationic) and non-ionic (non-ionic) polymers (such as MC, EC, HEC, HPC, HEMC, and HPMC) based on the separation of electrolytes or charges.

Synthetic gelling agents

Vinyls

Maleic anhydride and methyl vinyl ether are synthetically copolymerized to create polymethyl vinyl ether. Polyethylene glycol is the most often utilized plasticizer in the synthesis of polymethyl vinyl ether hydrogels. When delivering different active chemical moieties to the eyes, carboxyvinyl polymers (Carbopol grades) are utilized as jellifying agents.

Others

Poly (ethylene oxide) is a synthetic polymer with a greater molecular weight and the same chemical structure as polyethylene glycol. Ethylene oxide is catalytically polymerized in the presence of metallic systems as a catalyst to create polyethylene oxide. The rate of dissolution and swelling, viscoelastic behavior,

and the degree and duration of bio adhesion can all vary depending on the molecular weight of polyethylene oxide. As a result, it is well-liked among bio adhesive dosage formulations [9,12,13].

FORMULATION

Table:1 Ingredients of Ondansetron and its Function

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	FUNCTIONS	EXAMPLE
1.	Ondansetron HCl	Active drug	-
2.	Gelling agent / polymer	Base & viscosity modifier	HPMC (Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose), Sodium CMC, Pectin, Carbopol 934, Gelatin, Sodium alginate
3.	Plasticizer	Provides flexibility, prevents cracking	Glycerol, Propylene glycol, PEG 400
4.	Sweetener	Improves taste	Sucralose, Aspartame, Sorbitol
5.	Flavoring agent	Mask bitter taste	Orange, Strawberry, Mint
6.	Preservative	Preventing microbial growth	Methyl paraben, Propyl paraben
7.	Buffer / pH adjuster	Maintains stability	Citric acid, Sodium citrate
8.	Purified water	Solvent	-

SUGAR SYRUP PREPARATION

I.P. 2007 states that 33.4% w/w sugar syrup was made as follows: 33.4 grams of sugar were precisely weighed using a digital electronic balance and then transferred to a 250 ml beaker. To obtain the supersaturated solution of sugar syrup, 16.6 grams of water were gradually added to it while being constantly stirred, and it was then heated over a heating mantle.

PREPARATION METHOD OF JELLY

- An accurate weight shall be taken of each element.
- To manufacture sugar syrup, 67.7 grams of sugar will be added to a beaker, then the amount will be increased to 100 milliliters.
- The gelling agent will be added to that solution while being continuously stirred, and it will be heated until it dissolves to the appropriate firmness.
- The gelling agent will be fully dissolved, followed by the addition of stabilizer and citric acid, which will be mixed once more to preserve pH and improve jelly softness, respectively, before boiling for a few minutes.
- The preservative will be added to the above-mentioned solution after it has boiled, and it will be well and evenly combined.
- After precisely weighing the medicine, it is dissolved in an appropriate vehicle and added before the jelly sets, completely mixing.
- After transferring the entire solution into molds, the molds were properly covered to prevent exposure to the outside environment, allowing the solution to cool and settle peacefully [14].

Table :2 Formulation of Jelly

EVALUATION PARAMETER

PHYSICAL APPEARANCE

Physical characteristics of the medicated jelly, including color, consistency, clarity, and texture were assessed. In light of patient acceptance and compliance, these tests are important [1,4]. After gently rubbing the medicated jelly sample between two fingers, the product's stickiness and grittiness were evaluated visually. [5].

pH

The final jelly's pH affects both its stability and flavor. The jelly's pH was measured at room temperature using a digital pH meter. For this, 50 milliliters of distilled water were mixed with 0.5 grams of jelly to create a 1% solution, and the pH was recorded [6,14].

VISCOSITY

The Brookfield viscometer (DV-E) was used to measure the jelly's viscosity. Spindle number four was utilized since the mechanism is non-Newtonian. Viscosity was tested at room temperature ($25\text{C}\pm 5\text{C}$) for two minutes at 1.5 rpm [15].

CONTENT UNIFORMITY

The content uniformity test is performed to make sure that each dosage form has the same quantity of drug ingredients, or the active pharmaceutical components of the batch. A 100 ug/ml solution was made by dissolving one medicated jelly from each formulation in 50 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8. To create 10, 15, and 20 ug/ml solutions, respectively, 10 ml of the previously mentioned solutions 1, 1.5, and 2 ml were mixed with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. A UV-visible

spectrophotometer will be used to measure the absorbance of each solution at 248 nm [7].

SPREADABILITY

The Multimer-recommended apparatus was built and utilized for the study to ascertain the formulations spreadability. It is composed of wooden blocks and two glass slides. While the lower slide is fastened to wooden blocks, the upper slide has one end connected to a weight pan and the other to a glass slide. A 1000-gram weight was placed over two slides containing 2.5 grams of jelly for five minutes to press the sample to a consistent thickness. Eighty grams of weight were placed inside the pan. Spreadability was measured by the number of seconds required to divide into two slides. A shorter time interval to traverse the 7.5 cm distance indicates better spreadability [15,16].

Spreadability was calculated by using following formula.

$$S = M \times L/T$$

Where,

S = spreadability,

M = weight tide to top slide

L =glass slide's length (7.5cm),

T = amount of time needed to separate two slides

STABILITY STUDY

After the samples were kept for three months at room temperature and at different temperatures (ranging from 0 to 80 degrees Celsius), stability study was evaluated in accordance with ICH requirements. The jelly sample's pH, viscosity, and appearance were assessed each month. After letting the samples equilibrate for two hours at 25°C, all measurements were taken. [9–10]

IN VITRO DISSOLUTION STUDY

Using a USP paddle-style device and 900 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer as the dissolution medium, Jadhav et al. carried out an in vitro dissolution study. The device was kept at 150 rpm and [37C±0.5 C]. In

a volumetric flask, 5 ml of the material was removed and diluted to 10 ml. After 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, and 60 minutes, an additional 5 ml was removed, and 6.8 phosphate buffer solution was used to maintain the sink condition. The drug content of the sample was measured using a UV spectrophotometer set to λ_{max} 248 nm. After measuring absorbance, the percentage of drug release was calculated [11,17].

STICKINESS AND GRITTIENESS

The medicated jelly sample was gently rubbed between two fingers, and its stickiness and grittiness were assessed visually.

CONCLUSION

A promising patient-friendly substitute for traditional dose forms used to treat nausea and vomiting is the creation and assessment of oral medicated jelly containing ondansetron hydrochloride. This review emphasizes the benefits of oral jellies, including better palatability, quicker start of action, ease of swallowing, and increased compliance-particularly for dysphagic, elderly, and pediatric patients. Achieving desired physicochemical qualities, such as ideal consistency, medication content homogeneity, pH, and stability, depends critically on the addition of appropriate gelling agents, sweeteners, stabilizers, and flavoring ingredients. Ondansetron jelly can accomplish quick disintegration, acceptable drug release profiles, and sufficient stability under varied storage circumstances, according to evaluation studies conducted across a variety of formulations. All things considered, oral medicated jelly offers a flexible way to administer ondansetron, which may enhance treatment results and patient compliance. Its application in contemporary pharmaceutical formulation may be expanded by additional study concentrating on large-scale manufacturing, taste-masking technology, and clinical performance.

REFERENCES

1. Cooper and Gun: Dispensing for Pharmaceutics. CBS Publishers & Distributors, Twelfth Edition, 2000.
2. Raja Manali M, Dhiren P. Shah: Oral Medicated Jelly: A Recent Advancement In Formulation, An

- International Journal Of Pharmaceutical Sciences (2016),13-20.
3. Shah B, Nayak B and Gaudani R: Formulation Development And Evaluation Of unit Moulded Polyherbal Jelly Useful in Memory Enhancement, Pharma Science Monitor (2012),3(4): 2723-2730.
 4. Dubey M: Design and Development of Oral Medicated Jelly Of Palonosetron Hydrochloride Paripex, Indian Journal Of Research (2015), 4(6): 253-255.
 5. Tushar V. Ahire, Avish D. Maru1, Mitesh P. Sonawane1, Prasad S. Bhamare: Formulation, development and evaluation of albendazole oral jellies, Asian Journal Of Pharmaceutical Sciences (2016), 3(7): 706-712.
 6. Dr. Zankhana Sheth, Mahendrakumar Dubey: Design and Development of Oral Medicated Jelly of Palonosetron Hydrochloride (2015),4(6):253-255.
 7. Anand Ambekar1, Ajaykartik2, Vinay B: Preclinical Study of Ketoconazole Orotentive Medicated Jelly, British Journal Of Research (2015), 2(4): 122-131.
 8. Raja Manali M, Dhiren P. Shah, ORAL MEDICATED JELLY: A recent advancement in formulation, An International Journal Of Pharmaceutical Sciences (2016), 7(2): 13-20.
 9. T. Salunke, R. Mayee, V. Patil: Formulation And Evaluation Of Medicated Jelly Of Bitter Drugs (2013),3(5).
 10. P. Verma, A.S. Thakur, K. Deshmukh, Dr. A.K. Jha, S. Verma: Routes Of Drug Administration, International Journal of Pharmaceutical Studies and Research (2010), 54-59.
 11. Harada T, Yasuoka K, Sakurai M, Murase T, Owaki T: Development of a novel oral jelly formulation for elderly patients (2015), 135(2):249-54.
 12. Tiwari S, Batra N: Oral Drug Delivery System: A Review. American Journal of Life Science Research (2014), 2(1):27-35.
 13. Darade A D, Mundada A S: Oral medicated jellies as a emerging platform for oral drug delivery in Pediatrics, World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research (2021),10(6):1628-1647.
 14. Paras B. Pophalkar, R. B. Wakade, Sachin U. Hole, Chetan Y. Kadam, Rajnandni S. Suroshe and Wrushali A. Panchale: Development and evaluation of ondansetron medicated jelly, World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research (2018), 7(19):1252-1263.
 15. Aniket Jathar, Ram Ingale and Divvy Chonde: Innovation and testing of domperidone and ondansetron medicated jelly formulation, International Journal Of Pharmacy And Pharmaceutical Science (2025), 7(1): 01-09.
 16. AA D, AZBS B: Advantages of Jelly over Liquid Formulations for Pediatrics, Journal of Formulation Science & Bioavailability (2018),1(1).
 17. S. B. J: Development and Evaluation of Oral Medicated Jelly of Ondansetron Hydrochloride. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences (2017) ,1:1537-1549.
 18. Chhajed M, Chhajed A, Godhwani T, Tiwari D: Formulation Development and Evaluation of Unit Moulded Semisolid Jelly for Oral Administration as a Calcium Supplement, World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research(2012),1(3):626-634.

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